

Loading Methodology for a Capacity Constrained Job-Shop

Viraj Tyagi, Ajai Jain, P. K. Jain, Aarushi Jain

Abstract—This paper presents a genetic algorithm based loading methodology for a capacity constrained job-shop with the consideration of alternative process plans for each part to be produced. Performance analysis of the proposed methodology is carried out for two case studies by considering two different manufacturing scenarios. Results obtained indicate that the methodology is quite effective in improving the shop load balance, and hence, it can be included in the frameworks of manufacturing planning systems of job-shop oriented industries.

Keywords—Manufacturing planning, loading, genetic algorithm, Job-Shop.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN manufacturing industries, Manufacturing Planning and Control (MPC) systems are used for cost effective management of various activities related to the manufacturing of the products. MPC deals with the complex manufacturing problems such as large product mix and short lead times; moreover, it ensures that acceptable quality products are delivered to the customers by the due dates that are mutually agreed by the customers and the firm. Reference [16] reviewed important MPC approaches and reported that shop loading was not considered adequately by most of the researchers in the past. Further, it was stated that a poorly loaded shop can never yield feasible production schedules. Infeasible production schedule may create serious problems such as longer lead times, less throughput, late deliveries, high work-in-process, longer queues at machines and lower machines utilization at the shop floor [2], [5], [11]. Ultimately, it makes the manufacturing activities inefficient and costly. Thus, shop loading is crucial for efficient working of manufacturing industries. In the present work, shop loading refers to the assignment of various operations of parts under consideration to the available machines of job-shop.

Traditionally, parts that are to be produced are available with Single Process Plan (SPP). A traditional SPP contains only one sequence of operations as well as machines on which these operations are to be performed [6]. Usually, SPPs are not able to cope up with the uncertain conditions such as machine breakdown, non-availability of materials and/or tools that are usually present at the shop floor. The problems associated

with SPP can be overcome by ensuring the availability of Multiple Process Plans (MPP) for each part. Moreover, shop loading can be optimized in the presence of MPP. In the present paper, loading problem of a capacity constrained job-shop has been addressed in the presence of MPP for each part to be produced. Job-shop is considered, since a large number of small and medium companies operate, today, in job-shop environment. Job-Shop loading problem is considered to be a “combinatorial optimization” type, and such problems can be effectively addressed by modern heuristic techniques such as Genetic Algorithm (GA), tabu-search and simulated annealing [7]. GA shows better performance in global search and therefore, widely applied to solve the problems related to manufacturing planning [2], [10], [15].

This paper presents a GA based methodology for balancing work load of job shop in which capacity is constrained and alternative process plans (i.e. MPP) for each part type are available.

II. LOADING METHODOLOGY

Important aspects of the proposed methodology are briefly discussed as follows:

A. Capacity Feasibility of MPS

First of all, the proposed methodology ensures that sufficient capacity of job-shop under consideration is available to produce the parts of given Master Production Schedule (MPS) for a planning horizon of eight weeks. The shop utilization levels, best process plans, and due dates of parts are used to ensure that given MPS is feasible from the capacity consideration of given job-shop. The machines required to process a given part are considered to be available up to Net Available Time (NAT). NAT of a part is computed by multiplying the due date of part under consideration with the shop utilization level. For a part to be feasible from the job-shop capacity view point, load status of any machine as required by the best process plan of part under consideration, should be less than or equal to NAT of the part. If for any part, capacity of any machine is found insufficient, the part is removed from the given MPS. Thus, shop loading is carried out for a capacity feasible MPS. Further, GA is utilized in order to balance the work load of job-shop with the consideration of MPP for each part to be produced.

B. Shop Loading Methodology

GA is basically a computerized search algorithm that is inspired by the Darwin’s theory of survival of the fittest. The present work uses permutation type of encoding. In this scheme of representation, part is combined together with its

Viraj Tyagi is with Kurukshetra Institute of Technology & Management, Kurukshetra, India.

Ajai Jain is with National Institute of Technology, Kurukshetra, India (corresponding author, phone: +91-1744233464; fax: +91-1744-238050; e-mail ajaijain12@gmail.com).

P.K. Jain is with Indian Institute of Technology, Roorkee, India.

Aarushi Jain is with Fiserv India Pvt. Ltd, Noida, India.

their best process plans, and alternative process plans are usually not available, whereas in MPP environment, alternative process plans for each part are available. Thus, before scheduling the parts on machines, shop loading can be optimized for the given objective. In the present work, four MPPs are considered and these are ranked on the basis of the minimum total production time criterion; thus, process plan that takes minimum time to produce a part is ranked as best process plan.

Table II presents the fitness values of system balance for all eight weeks of the planning horizon under SPP as well as MPP environment for the considered case studies. It reveals that higher system balance is obtained in MPP environment as compared to SPP environment. For example, for case study 1 and at 70% shop utilization level, average fitness value of system balance is 0.6744 in MPP environment which is much

higher than 0.2937 of SPP environment. Similarly, for case study 2 and at 90% shop utilization level, system balance is 0.6651 in MPP environment as compared to 0.2283 of SPP environment. The proposed methodology attempts to improve the load balance among the machines of job-shop, and thus, higher average fitness values are obtained for MPP environment. This is true for all other scenarios as well, as indicated by Table II. Further, in some scenarios of SPP environment, very poor system balance is found as indicated by negative system balance. For example, for week 5 of case study 1, values of system balance are -0.0326, -0.0515, and -0.0515 at 70%, 80%, and 90% shop utilization levels, respectively. It happens in such a situation when $SU_{ind} > SU_{max}$, indicating that the load among the machines is highly unbalanced.

TABLE II
 SYSTEM BALANCE IN SPP AND MPP ENVIRONMENTS

Case Study	Week	System Balance (Fitness Values)					
		SPP Environment			MPP Environment		
		Shop Utilization Level (%)					
		70	80	90	70	80	90
1	1	0.3759	0.3759	0.3759	0.6478	0.6478	0.6478
	2	0.4321	0.4321	0.4321	0.6460	0.6460	0.6460
	3	0.4064	0.4064	0.4064	0.6645	0.6645	0.6645
	4	0.1816	0.1816	0.1816	0.7265	0.7265	0.7265
	5	-0.0326	-0.0515	-0.0515	0.8064	0.7331	0.7331
	6	0.0656	-0.0944	-0.0944	0.6494	0.4759	0.4759
	7	0.3879	0.2572	0.0593	0.5258	0.8401	0.8824
	8	0.5330	0.3408	0.0261	0.7289	0.7507	0.8862
	Average Fitness Value	0.2937	0.2310	0.1669	0.6744	0.6852	0.7078
2	1	0.6749	0.6749	0.6749	0.8283	0.8283	0.8283
	2	0.3316	0.3316	0.3316	0.5578	0.5578	0.5578
	3	0.4692	0.4692	0.4692	0.6103	0.6103	0.6103
	4	0.2380	0.2380	0.2380	0.6011	0.6011	0.6011
	5	0.1030	0.1101	0.1101	0.4837	0.6572	0.6572
	6	0.1776	-0.0677	-0.0677	0.7545	0.6151	0.6151
	7	0.3437	0.0555	-0.0494	0.6337	0.6812	0.6599
	8	0.5674	0.2792	0.1201	0.8546	0.8332	0.7910
	Average Fitness Value	0.3632	0.2613	0.2283	0.6655	0.6730	0.6651

In MPP environment, higher system balance is obtained due to the fact that alternative machines are available during shop loading. Ultimately, higher system balance yields feasible and efficient production schedules for the shop floor implementation [13]. Further, it is important to mention that in order to achieve higher system balance, process plan selected for a part may be different from one week to another.

Thus, it can be concluded that the proposed methodology is quite effective for balancing the job-shop load. Moreover, it can be included in the frameworks of manufacturing planning systems with the aim to manage operational problems of job-shop oriented industries, especially when alternative process plans are available for parts to be produced.

REFERENCES

- [1] Anderson E J and Ferris M C (1994), "Genetic algorithms for combinatorial optimization assembly line balancing problem", *ORSA Journal of Computing*, Vol. 6, pp. 161-173.
- [2] Chen K and Ji P (2007), "A mixed integer programming model for advanced planning and scheduling (APS)", *European Journal of Operational Research*, Vol. 181, pp. 515-522.
- [3] Deb K (2006), "Optimization for Engineering Design, Algorithms and Examples", Prentice-Hall of India, ND.
- [4] De Jong K A (1975), "An analysis of the behavior of a class of genetic adaptive systems", Doctoral Dissertation, University of Michigan, Dissertation Abstracts International, 36(10), 5140 B (University Microfilms No. 76-9381)
- [5] Ebadian M, Rabbani M, Torabi S A and Jolai F (2009), "Hierarchical production planning and scheduling in make-to-order environments: reaching short and reliable delivery dates", *International Journal of Production Research*, Vol. 47, No. 20, pp. 5761-5789.
- [6] Jain A (2003), "Integration of process planning and scheduling", Ph. D Dissertation, Unpublished, Faculty of Engineering and Technology, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra.
- [7] Kumar N and Shanker K (2000), "A genetic algorithm for FMS part-

- type selection and machine loading”, *International Journal of Production Research*, Vol. 38, No. 16, pp. 3861-3887.
- [8] Li W D and McMahon C A (2007), “A simulated annealing based optimization approach for integrated process planning and scheduling”, *International Journal of Computer Integrated Manufacturing*, Vol. 20, No. 1, pp. 80-95.
- [9] Mitchell M (2002), “An Introduction to Genetic Algorithms”, Prentice-Hall of India, ND.
- [10] Moon C, Seo Y, Yun Y and Gen M (2006), “Adaptive genetic algorithm for advanced planning in manufacturing supply chain”, *Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing*, Vol.17, pp.509-522.
- [11] Ozturk C and OrnekA M (2014), “Operational Extended Model Formulations for Advanced Planning and Scheduling Systems”, *Applied Mathematical Modelling*, Vol. 38, No. 1, pp. 181-195.
- [12] Tiwari M K and Vidyarthi N K (2000), “Solving machine loading problem in a flexible manufacturing system using a genetic algorithm based heuristic approach”, *International Journal of Production Research*, Vol. 38, No. 14, pp. 3357-3384.
- [13] Tyagi V (2013) “Integration of manufacturing planning functions” Ph.D Dissertation, Unpublished, Mechanical Engineering Department, National Institute of Technology, Kurukshetra.
- [14] Vinod V and Sridharan R (2008), “Scheduling a dynamic job shop production system with sequence-dependent setups: An experimental study”, *Robotics and Computer Integrated Manufacturing*, Vol. 24, pp. 435-449.
- [15] Zhang X D and Yan H S (2005), “Integrated optimization of production planning and scheduling for a kind of job shop”, *International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, Vol. 26, pp. 876-886.
- [16] Zijm W H M (2000), “Towards Intelligent Manufacturing Planning and Control Systems”, *OR Spectrum*, Vol. 22, pp. 313-345.